

MECHANISMS OF MANIPULATION IN INTERNET COMMUNICATIONS

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Annotation: *The article highlights the problems of manipulation in Internet communications, determining their features and impact on the audience in the context of socio-political processes.*

Key words: *manipulation, mass media, Internet, communication, audience.*

Manipulation as a social phenomenon is today a widely discussed topic of humanitarian research. Interest in the topic is caused by many factors: the political and economic situation in the country and in the world, the prevalence of manipulative phenomena and the availability of means of influence.

As you know, manipulations are a certain system of scenarios, algorithms, and techniques directly related to the implementation of the goals of stakeholders, which can affect the activities and lives of not only an individual or a certain social group, but can affect large public entities of a city, region, country or even the world, bringing significant dividends to the initiators.

In such a global context of vision of the problem, it is first of all important to point to the mass media (media), acting at the same time both as an environment and as a means of manipulative influence. Today, the media are an integral part of society. They inform the public on an hourly basis about the events taking place both in a single territory and in the world. Accordingly, the media have the opportunity to influence all social processes in it.

Information circulating in society penetrates and covers, of course, all strata of society, influencing the content of activity and life, as well as the dynamics of social processes. We have long been living according to the scheme "if you don't know the latest news, you lose", because it is awareness that determines what needs to be done today, and what is no longer relevant at the moment. This confirms the oft-mentioned "agenda-setting" theory, which is that it is the media that determines our agenda and what we will do. Do not forget about the Pygmalion effect, which consists in the fact that in anticipation of some kind of prophecy, an event that we have become aware of, with all our actions, without even realizing it, we contribute to its occurrence.

The Internet has become another important channel for the dissemination of information in society today. The media in our time are inextricably linked with the Internet - each publication, in order to increase popularity and "survive" in the market,

must have its own electronic version and place new information first of all in it. Traditional media (newspapers, radio) are simply not able to compete, given the difficulty of censoring the Internet, which makes them the main information source of our time.

Observing the processes of dissemination of information and "manipulative intrusions", many citizens seek to resist them, to inform other people about the existence of such phenomena. It is worth mentioning that quite recently, the well-known Elon Musk announced the Pravda service, the purpose of which is to assess the truth of news articles and track the trust rating of each journalist, editor and publication on the Internet [2]. This only emphasizes the importance of the problem of manipulative influences in modern society and specifically in the field of Internet communications, and, accordingly, the need to study it.

Do not forget about the reasons for the appearance of manipulations, people's gullibility towards them. In the political context and the media as an apparatus, a "mouthpiece" in politics, manipulations are brought to life because of the hope for change. Sometimes we can learn about a "fake" only after revealing its essence and myth-making foundations.

This became possible due to the low psychological culture of certain categories, strata of society. It is on them that the calculation of "strategists" and "businessmen" who plan and implement the scenarios of certain actions is based. In particular, the issues of tracking / preventing manipulation in new, constantly updated media of mass communication are not well developed - this is the Internet and individual services based on it (forums, blogs, social networks, etc.).

It should be noted that at present in our country the results of scientific activity in the field of psychology are not being sufficiently introduced (compared, for example, with European countries) to the level of everyday life of citizens. The recent case of the Telegram messenger and its blocking is a good example of the insufficient development of the mechanisms of information impact on the masses of some state bodies and, as a result, poor coverage of their position and manipulation of information in Internet communications. In the presence of many online publications that defended the side of the service and described its positive aspects, this information only contributed to the emergence of user interest and attracting additional audience to the service.

Speaking of manipulation, it is necessary to clarify the understanding of this term. Thus, based on the etymological analysis of E.L. Dotsenko of this concept, considered by various domestic and foreign authors [3], we can conclude that manipulation is a hidden psychological impact on an individual or group (object of control) by the manipulator, in order to change their behavior, activities in which the goals of the manipulator are realized. . In this case, harm, damage or other negative consequences for the object of manipulation, in principle, may be absent.

Based on the environment of existence and the operation of the manipulations we are interested in, it is worth noting that information in Internet communication is distributed en masse. A.A. Suvorov notes that the Internet was obtained from the merger of the main types of mass communication (printed word, radio, television), which is its synthetic nature. The second feature of the Internet is its expansive nature of development - it replaces the previously familiar methods of obtaining information. To access a wide audience, the media split up information flows before publication, which leads to visibility and ease of perception. In our opinion, this is often displayed in short titles of articles that describe the event as much as possible from the necessary point of view of the author; "unofficial" type of information transmission to the user, in the form of his usual daily communication; using the features of the environment (a large amount of constantly updated information) to generate content that can "hook" the user in a short time - pictures, memes, demotivators, etc. A.A. Suvorov also notes the high speed of dissemination of information on the Internet, which weakens its control and censorship and emphasizes the mass nature of the phenomenon. From this, the author highlights the last characteristic - high manipulative potential, prevailing over all other types of media due to the ease of managing information flows [5].

It is logical to assume that Internet communication, which emerged from classical mass communication, received its own differences from the latter due to the constant development and introduction of new environments and technological innovations. According to S.V. Volodenkov, Internet communication currently has some content, structural and technological features [6], which acquire important functions in the context of the manipulative process:

1. Structured audience. It follows from the important functions of the Internet (finding the necessary information and connecting people of the same interests over long distances). With the help of manipulations, it is possible to influence specific audiences, groups of people, for example: with the help of frequent media reminders in social networks. networks about the news about the creation of the Development Strategy in the Nizhny Novgorod region and its public discussion, entrepreneurs scattered throughout the region are uniting and uniting them to find an economic consensus.

2. "Horizontal" communication. Any person on the Internet is a full-fledged subject of communication with great freedom of expression. As a result, information not only reaches a specific addressee, but also spreads further, to other users, which is often used in technologies of emotional "infection" of the masses. A good example here is Donald Trump's Twitter account, which makes it possible to speak directly and more directly, without intermediaries, with an audience of voters, stating his point of view in a timely manner. This strategy allowed him to get rid of journalists and achieve greater popularity through "informal" dialogues with the audience.

3. Custom content generation. The participants of Internet communication themselves bring new content to their sites in the course of communication, which triggers a further reaction in the form of downloading "response" content by other users.

4. The influence of user ratings on the perception of messages. Strange as it may seem, but it is this factor that today becomes the key in determining opinion leaders, their popularity - messages with the highest rating deserve more trust.

5. Extraterritoriality. It is possible to become a member of Internet communication from almost every point of the globe if you have access to the Internet.

6. High mobilization potential. Due to highly developed communities, "horizontal" and the speed of dissemination of information, the response of users comes in a short time.

7. The influence of the Internet on the traditional political communication space. There is a noticeable trend that Internet users are becoming the most active part of the population, contributing to the emergence and development of political events. One of the reflections of this phenomenon was the emergence of the Council of Bloggers under the State Duma - leaders of public opinion that influence the masses and have a strong influence on the situation in the country.

8. Unlimited. The amount of information on the Internet is limited only by the storage capacity of the servers. Thus, the flow of manipulation can be practically unlimited in volume.

9. Targeting. Using the available metrics services, trackers, advertising identifiers, etc., a user profile is created with various companies, which contributes to the provision of information related to his interests, requests, but also indirectly manipulates his opinion - leads to the "imposition" of certain views.

10. Multimedia. The basis of the current Internet is the visibility and attractiveness of information. Support for all known data formats to meet the needs of the user contributes to this.

11. Extemporality. The presence of services such as web archives, search engine cache, page copies, as well as various means to counteract blocking, allow you to access most of the necessary information at any time.

12. Efficiency. On the Internet, time limits for working with information are only related to the operation of the technology that provides these services, and therefore there is also the possibility of quick editing / changing any information uploaded to public access.

13. Interactivity. On various resources, users can interact with each other using built-in tools and functions. Also, this feature can be used to create ads based on user interaction. For example, in a playful way, because, as you know, information is well absorbed when it is presented in an understandable and intelligible form that will interest the recipient.

14. These characteristics reveal the Internet as a unique communication space used in various areas of human life (development of social contacts, business relations, promotion of one's views and ideas) to generate information content, distribute it among users, form collective meanings in the process of horizontal information and communication interaction, as well as to mobilize the network community.

An important component of Internet communication manipulations is their mechanism. Initially, it should be noted that there is a wide range in the interpretation of the concepts of "mechanism", "method", "technology", "method", "technique", which is found in various scientific works. Which introduces a certain complexity both in understanding the author's position and in the process of generalizing and classifying the material.

The most attractive point of view regarding the nature of psychological mechanisms is to understand them as the very basis of a psychological phenomenon, a means of explaining the complex through the simple, which allows us to understand the whole scheme of this phenomenon. Therefore, the psychological mechanism of manipulation is a set of psychological (cognitive, emotional) processes and phenomena that precede and provide manipulation, and also arise after its implementation. The classification of psychological mechanisms of manipulation, presented in the work of D.G. Trunov [6], is generalized and universal in relation to various types of communication, including communication on the Internet.

The first mechanism is "impact on the emotional state of the partner." Since the emotional sphere of a person is one of the main motivating factors for his activity, then, depending on the goals of the manipulator, it is important to effectively promote the manifestation of certain feelings. Thus, coverage of information in a negative way often contributes to the manifestation of extreme emotional reactions of aggression among the targeted audience.

The second mechanism is "resource manipulation". Much in communication depends on the status and position of its members. In the environment of Internet communications, this factor has a special role. The number of subscribers, rating, ratings, and other criteria reflect the popularity, "weight" of the translator. In this case, the manipulator can use the "resources" of his account to obtain the desired result. The third mechanism is "exploitation of the personal characteristics of the object of manipulation." There are no perfect people, everyone has their own characteristics, weaknesses, expressed in qualities, needs, interests, values, habits, feelings. It is them that the manipulator primarily uses for its own purposes. In Internet communication, it is more difficult to determine them, because much of this can only be learned through direct communication, from verbal and non-verbal means of communication, etc. The final mechanism is "use of relationships". The subject of manipulation in the course of Internet communication can, through various forms of communication, use an indirect variant of influence through the involvement of

the environment of the manipulated - other users. Thus, supporters of the opinion contribute to the reduction of defending the recipient's own position.

It should be noted the opinion of G.A. Kopnina regarding speech manipulation and its types [4]. Highlighting the manipulation of images, conventional manipulation, operational-subject manipulation, exploitation of the personality, manipulation of spirituality, manipulation through the audiometric channel, the author indirectly names and characterizes the psychological mechanisms through which these effects are realized. Manipulation occurs either through the cognitive processes of the individual, or through stereotypes and attitudes, where the key in each case is one of them, a kind of "access point" to the consciousness of the individual, which becomes very clear in the context of information technology.

Thus, the Internet is a unique space with a set of unique characteristics that make it universal for the manifestation and development of all known human relationships. In the Internet space, a special generation of information content is possible, its distribution among users, the formation of collective meanings in the process of horizontal information and communication interaction. Because of this, Internet communication is an important and effective means of political activity and conveying one's own positions and views, points of view to the electorate, and, accordingly, fighting for it. The timely opening of manipulative algorithms and schemes makes it possible to prevent and hinder their impact, to put into practice the principles of justice, legality and, above all, humanity. As in any learning process, understanding the phenomenon of manipulation begins with the basics, its simplest components - mechanisms. Contributing to the understanding of the essence of directed manipulative influence, we form the immunity of society as a whole and the younger generation, the main user of modern information technologies, in particular.

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